

K area of sites Samara

3223 2021
41
27

- Land K 84 - 20 rlands, ~~100m x 310~~ ~~100m x 310~~
- 5.68 hkt K 102A+B - 12 rlands - 270 x 210m.
- 1.5 hkt. K 125. - 2 rlands. - 170 x 80

~~20 x 400 x 40~~

Deh Ali, 25 km SE. → 100m x 100m | 1 hkt.
 40 km SE → 150 x 50m | $\frac{3}{4}$ hkt.

Sans Samar 2A | 2

K 145.B. Total area of K 145 - b is 43 $\frac{1}{2}$ hectares
 K 145B is 15 $\frac{1}{4}$ hectares.

2A

K 84 / K 102B / K 138. 370m x 350m.

no honey comb

no pedestals

~~K18~~

K84 has 20 Lardo

row type 2A

K102 has 12 Lardo unrecod collector

+ row type 2A

~~K18~~